

A Crime, Two Stolen Cars, and the Fate of Actors and Objects: Violence and Automobile Theft in Rio de Janeiro.

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Currently, the state of Rio de Janeiro has an estimated population of 17.2 million people (IBGE, PNAD-C 2024) and a fleet of 7.9 million registered vehicles – the fifth largest in the country, behind only the states of São Paulo, Minas Gerais, Paraná, and Rio Grande do Sul (SENATRAM, 2024). In 2024, a total of 30.9 thousand vehicle thefts were recorded in the state (representing a 39% increase compared to 2023), corresponding to a rate of 174 incidents per 100,000 inhabitants – the highest among all Brazilian states (IBGE, 2022 Census; FBSP [2024] 2025).

Table 1 – Fleet, vehicle robbery and theft in the five Brazilian States with the largest populations.

	População (Pnad-C 2024)	Frota de Veiculos (*)	Roubo (N)	Furto (N)	Taxa de roubos por 100 mil habitantes	Taxa de furtos por 100 mil habitantes
Brasil	216.995.791	123.974.520	126.675	217.921	58	100
São Paulo	47.649.489	34.332.819	31.696	93.996	67	197
Minas Gerais	21.726.479	13.975.854	4.683	24.258	22	112
Rio de Janeiro	17.726.709	7.973.983	30.930	17.337	174	98
Bahia	15.109.674	5.389.511	11.131	6.690	74	44
Paraná	11.810.279	9.179.769	2.104	11.222	18	95

(*) All types of motor vehicles registered (fine or licensing) in the past 10 years. Source: FBSP [2024], 2025; BRAZIL, DENATRAN, 2024; IBGE, *National Household Sample Survey – Continuous (PNAD-C)*, cumulative first visits, 2024. Author's elaboration.

This high rate of car theft manifests itself in everyday life in Rio de Janeiro through episodes of violence widely reported in the media, which expose the fractures in social relations and the deep inequalities among the inhabitants of the state capital. One such case that marked the city's recent history was the **latrocínio** (robbery followed by murder) of the 64-year-old physician and plastic surgeon CS. Although much of the case's public resonance stemmed from the online presence of his son – the psychiatrist, YouTuber, and influencer IS, who has 1.5 million followers – the case became particularly significant for involving members of Rio's elite associated with the far right, individuals occupying different positions within the city's criminal factions, and for

exemplifying the typical trajectory and dynamics surrounding two stolen cars in Rio de Janeiro: a Renault Sandero Stepway and a Toyota Hilux SW4 (SUV).

On the morning of January 19, 2021, CS (64 years old) had his Toyota SW4 intercepted by a black Renault Sandero as he attempted to park in front of his clinic in Barra da Tijuca, in Rio de Janeiro's West Zone. Three men exited the Sandero, one of them armed. The doctor tried to grab and pin the assailant against the low wall bordering the canal along the avenue. Cornered, the gunman fired a shot that struck the doctor in the head, killing him instantly. Without hesitation, the shooter took control of the SUV and sped away, following the car carrying his accomplices.

On the same day, officers from Homicide Division and Pacifying Police Unit found the black Sandero – cloned vehicle – parked in the Turano *favela* area, 21 km away from the murder scene. At the time, TBS, 38 years old, was placed in preventive detention as a suspect after police found, at his residence, a backpack containing the doctor's belongings, a Toyota key, and two licenses plates intended for use in cloning the vehicle. The police also located the stolen vehicle, a Toyota SW4, parked on Martins Pena Street in Tijuca, near the Turano *favela* area.

Figure 1: Sandero Stepway Involved in the Commission of the Crime

Source: Civil Police release, published in an article by Rafaella Balieiro on the Band-Rio portal. Available at: <https://www.band.com.br/rio-de-janeiro/noticias/agentes-encontram-carro-criminosos-morte-claudio-marsili-16455476>. Accessed on October 21, 2025.

Figure 2: Stolen Toyota SW4 Vehicle

Source: Civil Police release, published in an article by Adriana Cruz on the Metropoles news portal. Available at: <https://www.metropoles.com/brasil/policia-encontra-carro-de-cirurgiao-plastico-morto-na-barra-da-tijuca>. Accessed on October 21, 2025.

Subsequent events confirmed that TBS had indeed fired the gun, but that was not all: the thief had connections to, and at the time was acting under the orders of, a larger criminal gang specialized in vehicle cloning and resale. This gang supplied stolen cars both across Brazil and abroad and was led by the former thief and Rio de Janeiro's most notorious car cloner, known as CML.

Currently 39 years old, CML became known in the Morro do Turano and within the Rio de Janeiro Civil Police due to his involvement in drug trafficking and his rivalry with another trafficker, Playboy (killed in 2015), gaining a reputation as the city's most notorious car thief. Established in territory protected by the Comando Vermelho, his clients grew over time, extending his services to fraudsters and even militias. According to one interviewee, at this stage the relationship with the faction becomes a commercial one, maintained as long as mutual benefits exist: "The guy who does this, cloning the car, 'is neither a criminal nor a thief'; he is a specialist in this, it's his business. He comes and offers the service to the guys on the hill." (Conversation with M, field diary, 05/02/2024).

This led him to stop taking part directly in the high-risk act of stealing cars and to move into coordinating an organization with a clearly defined division of labor, capable

of cloning a vehicle and dispatching it for delivery in as little as four hours. According to the Robbery and Theft of Automobiles Division of the Rio de Janeiro Civil Police, the group's work involved altering the chassis number, glass, engine, documents, and license plates. To approach perfection, the gang used off-the-shelf equipment and readily available technology capable of modifying vehicle numbers and codes in a way comparable to the work carried out by manufacturers.

Another aspect of the gang's operation was the sale of cloned vehicles online, with a team dedicated exclusively to online sales. The group became so well known that even fraudsters and car thieves in Rio de Janeiro began seeking them out to resell stolen vehicles. According to data from the Foundation of the Institute for Applied Economic Research (Fundação Instituto de Pesquisas Econômicas Aplicadas, Fipe), the main reference for vehicle prices in Brazil, a 2021 Toyota Hilux SW4, 4x2, Flex, 16V (similar to the stolen vehicle) had an average price of US\$ 43,794.05 (as of October 2025), equivalent to 155 minimum wages in Brazil. The 2021 Renault Sandero used in the execution of the crime had a lower value, US\$ 12,279.48, equivalent to 43.5 minimum wages.

The differences in size, power, status, and market value between the two vehicles help explain the divergent fates they are likely to encounter. The Toyota Hilux SW4 is highly sought after by thieves and traffickers – the so-called “carretões”: large SUVs that allow for high-speed driving, overcoming speed bumps in favelas, and transporting high-caliber firearms such as rifles. Many of these vehicles are appropriated by criminals for leisure, ostentation, and the commission of other crimes, including robberies, escapes, and incursions into rival territories. Other potential destinations for vehicles like the SW4 include other Brazilian states and rural areas of Bolivia and Paraguay, where pickups and utility vehicles similar to the stolen model typically cost around US\$ 60,000 and can be exchanged for approximately 7 kilograms of coca paste (Feltran, 2022).

These vehicles are stolen on order, cloned, and either sent to receivers or resold online at prices below market value. According to Delegate MCB, head of the DRFA, gangs like CML's “only work with vehicles worth more than R\$ 100,000 (US\$ 18,600) because the financial return is greater” (Dossares, 2021). For models valued at around US\$ 27,900, for example, the gang was able to sell them at an average price of US\$ 18,600 (65.8 minimum wages), a price attractive both to buyers and to the perpetrators of the crime, who were thus able to achieve economic gains exceeding those from selling a popular Vehicle.

These tragic events, taken as the starting point of the discussion developed here, reproduce in their outcome the political-ideological disputes and social inequalities that currently characterize Brazilian metropolises. The plastic surgeon from Rio de Janeiro's elite had his life cut short by a gunshot, that is, he became a victim of a pro-gun policy which his son – an influencer identified with the far right and self-described expert in personal development – considers the best solution to the country's public security problems.

For the perpetrators of the robbery, the punishments imposed by the Brazilian judicial and penal system offer few alternatives that do not involve continued engagement in criminal life. The shooter, TBS, who had a total of 13 criminal records, was convicted once again. He is currently imprisoned, having faded from public attention to become just another number in Brazil's prison population. CML was arrested on January 28, 2022, and returned to the news in February 2025 following the interception of messages he sent to the leaders of the Jacarepaguá drug trafficking network.

From inside prison, CML remains influential and actively participates in acquiring high-caliber rifles and ammunition through the CAC system (Collectors, Shooters, and Hunters): ironically a policy created by the Bolsonaro government (2018–2022) that claimed to combat crime but in practice strengthened the firepower of criminal factions. What the victim's heir and the mastermind of the robbery share is the exercise of leadership and the use of violence as a conflict mediation tool, a language both attempt to deploy to achieve their objectives.

References:

CRUZ, Adriana. Polícia encontra carro de cirurgião plástico morto na Barra da Tijuca. Metrôpoles. Rio de Janeiro, 19 out. 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.metropoles.com/brasil/policia-encontra-carro-de-cirurgiao-plastico-morto-na-barra-da-tijuca>. Acesso em 20/10/2025.

DOSSARES, T. Saiba quem é Tio Comel e como atua o clonador de carros de luxo que está por trás da morte de médico na Barra. Meia Hora, Notícias. Rio de Janeiro. Disponível em: <https://www.meiahora.com.br/geral/2021/10/6259979-saiba-quem-e-tio-comel-e-como-atua-o-clonador-de-carros-de-luxo-que-esta-por-tras-da-morte-do-medico-na-barra.html#foto=1>. Acesso em 21/10/2025

FELTRAN, Gabriel. "Globalization and Its Backroads". FELTRAN, Gabriel (Org) *Stolen Cars. A Journey Through São Paulo's Urban Conflict*. Series: IJURR studies in urban and social change book series. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2022, pp.190-207.

FÓRUM BRASILEIRO DE SEGURANÇA PÚBLICA. 19º Anuário Brasileiro de Segurança Pública. São Paulo: Fórum Brasileiro de Segurança Pública, 2025. Disponível em: <https://forumseguranca.org.br/publicacoes/anuario-brasileiro-de-seguranca-publica/>. Acesso em 20/08/2025.